

Clubroot in Danish winter rapeseed, caused by *Plasmodiophora brassicae*

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Front picture: Courtesy of Syngenta

The picture shows a recently merged winter rapeseed field, bought from a neighbouring dairy farmer. Knowing the acquired field had a history of severe clubroot incidence, the farmer chose to deploy a resistant cultivar SY Alister on this site (*left*) and DK Explicit on the rest of the merged field (*right*). The boundary was however misjudged, and the susceptible DK Explicit was sown on infested soil, inflicting severe yield losses in this patch.

Abstract

Winter rapeseed is an increasingly important crop in the Danish crop rotation of cereals, generating profitable oil and residuals used as animal feed in the large-scale production of livestock. Inflicted by an increasing occurrence of clubroot disease, capable of causing yield losses exceeding 50% this bachelor project aim to present a review of current knowledge on clubroot to facilitate an assessment of the threat.

The causative agent of clubroot *Plasmodiophora brassicae*, lately achieved a revised classification, believed to reside in the Rhizaria supergroup. Mediated by induced cytokinin and auxin phytohormones, *P. brassicae* manipulate host carbon metabolism and several physiological processes in the cortical infection stage, leading to the formation of root galls. Exceedingly persistent, resting spores of *P. brassicae* can endure more than 17 years without a susceptible host and subsequently infect a multitude of important agricultural crops and common weeds.

None of the available practices can achieve a solitary comprehensive control of clubroot, an integrated management strategy involving liming practices, crop rotation, drainage and resistant cultivars is therefore emphasized in conjunction with appropriate sanitary measures. Nonetheless, present management of clubroot is unsustainable, depending solely on a precautionary 1 in 5 crop rotation and deployment of resistant cultivars. Restrained by economic uncertainty in Danish agriculture and unawareness of clubroot is likely to constrain farmers from investing in long-term management strategies. Observations of declining efficacy in resistant cultivars is an immediate issue demanding a restrained usage until novel cultivars are introduced in near future. Measurement of clubroot is conducted at 2500 DKK per soil sample, applying a highly sensitive Rt-PCR protocol capable of detecting and quantifying *P. brassicae*. Development of an on-farm diagnostic kit is progressing, with monoclonal antibody based lateral flow device exhibiting potential as a rapid and cheap semi-quantitative alternative to Rt-PCR. Conclusively, a comprehensive national investigation of clubroot incidence in Denmark is emphasized as a precautionary measure to facilitate a timely large-scale address to clubroot if necessary.

Sammendrag

Dyrkning af vinterraps i sædskiftet med korn er en udbredt praksis i det danske landbrug, motiveret af den økonomiske gevinst ved rapsolien og, biprodukternes rolle som fodermiddel i den intensive husdyrproduktion. Forekomster af kålbrok-angreb i driften er et voksende problem og kan potentielt, forårsage udbyttetab på mere end 50%. Formålet med dette bachelor projekt er derfor at tilstræbe en samlet evaluering af tilgængelig viden i vurdering af kålbroks rolle som skadevolder i vinterrapsproduktionen.

Det sygdomsfremkaldende patogen af kålbrok *Plasmodiophora brassicae* taksonomi er fornyligt blevet revurderet, og arten forventes nu at tilhøre Rhizaria supergruppen. Medieret af plantehormonerne cytokinin og auxin manipulere *P. brassicae* værtens kulstof metabolisme og flere fysiologiske processer i korkcelleinfektionsstadiet, der giver ophav til det kølleformede rodsystem. Det persistente patogen producerer hvilespore, der kan bibeholde deres spiredygtighed i mere end 17 år og inficerer et utal af vigtige afgrøder og typiske ukrudtsarter i landbruget.

Ingen af de nuværende bekæmpelsesmetoder kan enkeltstående opnå kontrol af kålbrok, og en integreret strategi involverende kalkningspraksis, sædskifte, dræning og resistente sorter er derfor anbefalet; sammenholdt med tilstrækkelige sanitære foranstaltninger. Den nuværende bekæmpelsesstrategi af kålbrok er uholdbar, da den alene afhænger af et fireårigt sædskifte og anvendelse af resistente sorter. Økonomisk ustabilitet i det danske landbrug og ubevidsthed i håndteringen af kålbrok er sandsynlige faktorer der er årsag til den manglende investering i de langsigtede bekæmpelsesstrategier.

Faldende udbytter observeret i de resistente sorter, er et akut problem, og en tilbageholden anvendelse anbefales, indtil nye sorter introduceres på markedet. Analyse af kålbroksmitte tilbydes for 2500 DKK pr jordprøve, og udføres i en yderst sensitive Rt-PCR protokol i stand til at detektere og kvantificere *P. brassicae*. Udviklingen af et diagnoseværktøj til landmanden er i fremgang, og et monoklonal antistofbaseret *lateral flow device* vil i nær fremtid kunne tilbyde et hurtigt og billigt semi-kvantitativ alternativ til Rt-PCR. Der appelleres til en omfattende national undersøgelse af kålbroksmitte i Danmark, til rettidigt at kunne risikovurdere sygdommens omfang og om nødvendigt udarbejde en handlingsplan.

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List of abbreviations

AB	<i>Antibody</i>	HR	<i>Hypersensitive reaction</i>
BCA	<i>Biological control agent</i>	i.e.	<i>Id est, that is</i>
C_t	<i>Cycle threshold, PCR</i>	IAA	<i>Indole-3-acetic acid</i>
CI	<i>Cortical infection</i>	LFD	<i>Lateral flow device</i>
CK	<i>Cytokinin, class of phytohormones</i>	mAB	<i>Monoclonal antibody</i>
CR	<i>Clubroot resistant</i>	PZ	<i>Primary zoospore</i>
DSI	<i>Disease severity index</i>	qPCR	<i>Quantitative PCR, see Rt-PCR</i>
e.g.	<i>Exempli gratia, for example</i>	R&D	<i>Research and development</i>
ECD	<i>European Clubroot Differentials</i>	RHI	<i>Root hair infection</i>
ELISA	<i>Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay</i>	RS	<i>Resting spore</i>
GSF	<i>Germination stimulating factor</i>	Rt-PCR	<i>Real-time polymerase chain reaction</i>
GSL	<i>Glucosinolate</i>	SZ	<i>Secondary zoospore</i>
ha	<i>Hectare, 10.000 m²</i>	WR	<i>Winter rapeseed (Brassica napus ssp. napus)</i>

Introduction

In recent years, development of the political climate has had an increasing influence on how the arable land in Denmark is cultivated to secure production of food and sustainable energy in the future (Sehested and Søndergaard, 2014). Concurrently, the cultivation of winter oilseed rape (WR) (*Brassica napus ssp. napus*) has become an equivalently important break crop to cereals in the Danish farm rotations (SEGES, 2015), encouraged by rising profitability of rapeseed oil (Maribo et al., 2012). The oil is used for human consumption, or refined to a first grade biodiesel. Residual products of the oil extraction, rapeseed cake is an important animal feedstuff in the large-scale production of dairy cows and pigs in Denmark (Møller, 2010, Maribo et al., 2012). In 2013 the cultivation of rapeseed occupied an arable land of 177.200 hectares (ha) in Denmark, as illustrated in figure 1, including a negligible area of 1375 ha spring crop (FAOSTAT, 2015, DKStatistik, 2015).

Figure 1: Area of Rapeseed Cultivation in Denmark (FAOSTAT, 2015) from 1970 to 2013 k: Thousand

The WR crop is afflicted by several diseases in Denmark, of which black leg (*Anamorfo, Phoma lingam*), sclerotinia stem rot (*Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*), grey mold (*Botrytis cinerea*) and black spot (*Alternaria brassicae*) are the most prevalent (SEGES, 2015). Escalating incidences of clubroot disease in crops of the Brassicaceae family is equivalently an issue of mounting concern in the Danish WR cultivation (Personal communication, Gefion 2015). The increasing occurrence of severe clubroot attacks in the neighbouring countries Germany (Personal communication, JKI 2015) and UK (Burnett et al., 2013) inflicting substantial yield losses on the WR crop emphasize an necessity to address this particular disease.

The causative agent of clubroot, a soil-borne organism *Plasmodiophora brassicae* induces a formation of root galls, impairs nutrient uptake and growth leading to wilting or death of the infected plants, inflicting yield losses exceeding 50% in WR crops (Burnett et al., 2013). Renowned for its environmental resistant resting spores (RS), *P. brassicae* can endure for more than 17 years in the absence of a susceptible host (Wallenhammar, 1996), a trait that impedes a control of clubroot. The traditional management strategies in Denmark involves drainage, liming practices and an advisory crop rotation of one WR crop in five years (SEGES, 2015, Hobolth, 1977). Use of a crop rotation is nonetheless a difficult management tool hindered by RS longevity and the natural abundance of hosts to *P. brassicae* in both crops,

break crops and common weeds (Dixon, 2009b). Resistant cultivars are therefore a decisive control method to cut the yield losses. Concerning decline in control efficacy however urge a restrained usage to prolong the durability of resistance (Personal communication, SEGES 2015). Sufficient hygiene practice is equally emphasized as a precautionary measure to avoid dissipation of contaminated soil between fields (Hobolth, 1977).

The study of the obligate biotrophic organism *P. brassicae* has undergone a vast development in the recent years, enhanced by advances in cultivation techniques and analytic procedures (Wallenhammar et al., 2011, Wakeham, 2015). The aim of this bachelor project is to evaluate present knowledge in an assessment of clubroot disease importance in the Danish winter rapeseed production, with the following objectives:

- 1) Present recent knowledge on the biology of *P. brassicae*, with particular interest in clarifying the host interaction leading to symptom development.
- 2) Present recent R&D advances in detection and quantification of *P. brassicae*
- 3) Evaluate the possibility of introducing an on-farm diagnostic test of clubroot in Denmark.
- 4) Present an assessment of the current control methods available to manage clubroot in Danish WR cultivation.

Part 1. The biology of *Plasmodiophora brassicae*

The commencing spread of clubroot observed in recent years is a growing concern for Danish agriculture (Nielsen, 2014). Experience from neighbouring countries UK (Burnett et al., 2013) and Germany (Strehlow et al., 2014) indicates that rethinking the approach is necessary to address the issue. Achieving a profound knowledge of *P. brassicae* biology is likely to mediate an effective control. Through studies on the biology of *P. brassicae*, a targeted approach can effectively be designed to control the pathogen at vulnerable stages in its life cycle (Agarwal et al., 2009, Feng et al., 2012b).

In the following subsections, an effort to present recent knowledge of *P. brassicae* intricate life cycle has been conducted from this perspective.

1.1: Classification

At the discovery of *P. brassicae* Woronin as the causative agent of clubroot by Mikhail S. Woronin in 1878 (Tommerup and Ingram, 1971), the pathogen was placed in the fungi kingdom, and remained so for nearly a century (Nowicki, 1973). Woronin (1878) considered *Plasmodiophora* as one of the simplest Myxomycetes (slime molds) despite recognising several imperfections in the classification, cited in (Christensen, 2006). The traditional taxonomical classification, categorized organisms on their degree of key similarities in e.g. life cycle and morphology. Consistent with the slime molds, *P. brassicae* exhibit biflagellate zoospores and a plasmodial amoeboid stage (Agrios, 2005g).

Accumulation of controversies due to commencing advances in the molecular biology urged the necessity of a novel approach (Adl et al., 2005). This led to the development of a phylogenetic classification model categorizing on degree of evolutionary relation rather than the previous visual similarities. In modern phylogenetics *P. brassicae* is therefore commonly accepted to belong in the protist supergroup Rhizaria, with the taxonomy as seen in table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Classification of *Plasmodiophora brassicae* within the supergroup Rhizaria, after (Braselton and Bulman, 2014, Adl et al., 2005)

Domain	Eukarya
Supergroup	Rhizaria
Phylum	Cercozoa
Class	Phytomyxea
Order	Plasmodiophorida
Genus	<i>Plasmodiophora</i>
Specie	<i>P. brassicae</i>

Usage of the term protist must not be confused with the historical taxon Protista, named by Ernst Haeckel in 1866 (Madigan et al., 2015). Presently it is used to describe a major group of unicellular microorganisms without cell differentiation into tissues.

In the class of phytomyxea a unique type of nuclear division, designated cruciform division has been found (Braselton and Bulman, 2014). Through the mitotic metaphase the persistent nucleolus is elongated parallel to the spindle and perpendicular to the plate of chromatin, thus forming a cross like (cruciform) configuration as see in figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: *Plasmodiophora brassicae*. TEMG of cruciform division in sporogenic plasmodium in root of chinesecabbage. Nucleolus (N), Chromatin (C), Centrioles (Large arrows), Persistent membranes (Small arrows). (Photography courtesy of Dr. James P. Braselton, Ohio University).

Despite implementation of a phylogenetic model, the organisms still share a range of features indicative of their common descent (Madigan et al., 2015). The order of plasmodiophorids are characterized by; multinucleate plasmodia, biflagellate zoospores, environmental resistant resting spores (RS) and a intracellular biotrophic growth form (Braselton and Bulman, 2014). Several species residing in the order similarly inflict hypertropia and hypertrophy in the host organism (Braselton, 1995), all which will be thoroughly described in the following subsections.

A number of relatives to *P. brassicae* are similarly pathogenic, with diseases of significant agricultural impact like e.g. powdery scab caused by *Spongospora subterranea* on the potato plant (*Solanum tuberosum*) (Merz and Falloon, 2009). Symptoms of the disease is the formation of superficial lesion, leaving the tuber not only vulnerable to secondary infections upon storage but also in severe cases unsuitable for sale. In addition to this, the pathogen function as a vector, transmitting the *Potatoe Mop-Top Virus* (PMTV), further reducing yield and quality of the crop. Another relative to *P. brassicae* similarly residing in the Plasmodiophorida order is *Polymyxa graminis* and *Polymyxa betae*, causal agent behind the transmission of barley- and beet necrotic yellow vein viruses (Agrios, 2005g).

1.2: Life Cycle

As a member of phytomyxea, the life cycle of *P. brassicae* has proven difficult to describe due to the obligat, intracellular biotrophic life form characteristic of the class (Braselton and Bulman, 2014). Obtained by a course of subsequent advances in cultural techniques has enabled an in-vitro cultivation of *P. brassicae* infected callus or root hair cells (Kageyama and Asano, 2006, Tommerup and Ingram, 1971), solving the previous limitation.

The life cycle of *P. brassicae* as seen in figure 1.2 involves three stages; a primary root hair infection (RHI), secondary cortical infection (CI) and intermediate soil survival (Agrios, 2005g). In this subsection, an overview of the main events in the life cycle will be presented, followed by in depth reviews of the three phases in the consequent subsections.

Figure 1.2: Disease cycle of clubroot of crucifers caused by *Plasmodiophora brassicae*. (Agrios, 2005g)

The germination of an resting spore (RS) in the intermediate soil survival stage leads to the release of a single 2.8-5.9 μm long, spindle shaped or pyriform, uninucleate, primary zoospore (PZ) (Braselton and Bulman, 2014). Having two heterologous flagella, the cell is motile, enabling it to transport itself through the soil water in the pursuit of a susceptible host. A successful encounter triggers a cascade of events; retraction of flagella, encystation on root hair cell and mobilization of storage components in the initiation of the RHI, proceeding as depicted in figure 1.21 (Aist and Williams, 1971). Formation of a dense projectile-like structure (Satchel), within a tubular cavity (Rohr) penetrates the cell wall through hydrostatic pressure, leading to the injection of cyst protoplasm in the host root hair cell, as illustrated in figure 1.21 (Braselton and Bulman, 2014).

Figure 1.21: Diagrammatic summary of the sequences of events during penetration of the host by *Plasmodiophora brassicae*. (A) Cyst vacuole not yet enlarged, (B) Cyst vacuole enlarges and small adhesorium appears, (C) Stylet punctures host cell wall, (D) Penetration has occurred and the host protoplasm has deposited a papilla at the penetration site. After (Aist and Williams, 1971).

This mechanical penetration induces the production of a callose papilla, interpreted as a wound-healing response of the host plant. These prepenetration events illustrated in figure 1.21 takes an estimated two hours, initiating the primary phase of *P. brassicae* life cycle, as depicted in the figure 1.22 (McDonald et al., 2014).

Figure 1.22: Infection of root hair (arrow) on canola root inoculated with secondary zoospores of pathotype 6 of *Plasmodiophora brassicae* (McDonald et al., 2014).

At this stage the *P. brassicae* resembles an amoeboid mass referred to as the primary plasmodia, and through numerous of mitotic cruciform divisions it become multinucleate (Braselton, 1995, Tommerup and Ingram, 1971). Synchronous to this event the plasmodia proliferates, presumably spreading by cytoplasmic streaming to neighbouring cells of the root hair (Kageyama and Asano, 2006). After a given time the plasmodia cleaves, creating numerous multinucleate portions that each develops into a zoosporangia (Agrios, 2005g), a sequence of processes referred to as the sporangial phase. The zoosporangium contains 4-16 secondary zoospores (SZ) at maturity, visually undistinguishable from the previous PZ (Kageyama and Asano, 2009). Elapsed time from primary infection to the dissipation of SZ is approximately five days given the optimal conditions (McDonald et al., 2014).

Observation of binucleate zoospores lead to the interpretation that SZ fuse through plasmogamy to form a zygote, as depicted in figure 1.2 (Tommerup and Ingram, 1971, Mehrotra and Aneja, 1990). Occurrence of karyogamy in the fused spores is however not documented, and remains an major unsolved aspect of the life cycle (Braselton and Bulman, 2014). The released SZ invades the cortical cells of a host, commencing the secondary stage of the life cycle as depicted in figure 1.23 (Feng et al., 2012b).

Figure 1.23: Secondary infection on ryegrass 35 days after inoculation with secondary zoospores from ryegrass. Arrows indicate the secondary plasmodia. Bar = 10 μ m. (Feng et al., 2012b)

At this stage the developing secondary plasmodia induces an overgrowth of the root cells referred to as hypertrophy; abnormal cell enlargement, and hyperplasia; increased cell division rate (Kageyama and Asano, 2009). Development of large root galls is therefore a distinctive sign of a severe infection, giving the disease its name “club” root. Furthermore, the secondary plasmodia infiltrates the vascular tissue, absorbing nutrients and interfering with the translocation structure in the plant. Arising from this interaction, wilting and stunted growth of aerial parts are common symptoms of a severely infected plant (Agrios, 2005g).

Proliferation of the secondary plasmodia is terminated by a non-cruciform and evidently meiotic division, preceding the protoplasm cleavage in the formation of resting spores (Braselton and Bulman, 2014). Despite evidence of karyogamy this sequence of events referred to as the sporogenic phase sustain a genetic diversity and progression in the population (Braselton, 1995). The spore cell wall contain chitin a distinctive component in fungi, and are covered with spines and warts on their surface (Mehrotra and Aneja, 1990).

A morphological characteristic of *P. brassicae* is absence of RS organization in clusters referred to as sporosori, observed in e.g. *S. subterranea*, as illustrated in figure 1.24 (Braselton, 1995, Falloon et al., 2011). Instead they are found unorganized, lying freely throughout the cortical cells of an infected host, as illustrated in figure 1.25 (Mehrotra and Aneja, 1990).

Figure 1.24: (Left) Light micrographs of representative sporosori of *Spongospora subterranea* f. sp. *subterranea* from powdery scab lesions on potatoe tubers (cv "Agria", New Zealand 2004) (Falloon et al., 2011)

Figure 1.25: (Right) Scanning electron macrograph of resting spores of *Plasmodiophora brassicae* within cells on clubroots (Agrios, 2005g).

Completing the life cycle, RS are dissipated to the soil environment through disintegration of the host root tissue. Renowned for its persistence, the perennating spore can remain viable for at least 17 years in this stage, until a susceptible host comes of range (Wallenhammar, 1996). Mapping the time elapsed in each of the individual stages is difficult, mostly impeded by the biotrophic nature of the pathogen (Agarwal et al., 2009). Several studies has addressed this subject, commonly recognizing RHI to take place from day 4 to 7 after inoculation in infested soil, and subsequently CI from day 9 to 24 (Tommerup and Ingram, 1971, Agarwal et al., 2009). The rate of infection development is nonetheless highly variable, influenced by a range of factors, e.g. e.g. temperature, edaphic factors i.e. chemical and physical properties of the soil, pathotype virulence, host susceptibility etc. Usage of these approximations should therefore be done with caution, as a rough overview of the infection progression leading to clubroot disease.

1.3: Survival in Soil

The resting spore of *P. brassicae* is renowned for its environmental resistance, capable of surviving more than 17 years in the soil without a susceptible host (Wallenhammar, 1996). A trait that has made an efficient control of the clubroot disease most demanding. Despite the longevity, a dormant spore is able to respond rapidly to the presence of a compatible host, initiating the germination (Dixon, 2009b). The study of this intermediary stage of *P. brassicae*s life cycle is likely to play a decisive role in the pursuit of a more effective clubroot control. In this subsection, the trigger mechanism behind RS germination will be the primary topic, reviewing the existing knowledge on the field.

The influence of environmental parameters in the initiation of germination was observed in a research conducted nearly 100 years ago by Chupp (1917), it concluding that a temperature of 14°C was required for RS germination (Gossen et al., 2013). Successive studies moderately supported this observation, demonstrating a substantial reduction in RS germination and subsequent RHI at 10-15°C (Sharma et al., 2011c), whereas optimum is at 20-25°C (Gossen et al., 2013).

Initiation of RS germination as a response to host root exudates was the first stimuli postulated, and equivalently proven (Macfarlane, 1970). Succeeding observations of germination in the presence of non-host plants conflicts with this theory (Hellmers, 1976), indicative of a more intricate response mechanism. A Swedish research group recently conducted a study on this subject, cultivating perennial ryegrass, leek, red clover and winter rye in *P. brassicae* infested soil (Friberg et al., 2005). Their observations demonstrated a non-specific RS spore germination, as illustrated in figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3: Percentage germinated spores of *P. brassicae* in exudate solution from perennial ryegrass (*L. perenne* ■), Chine cabbage (*B. rapa* var. *pekensis* ◆), leek (*A. porrum* ▲), red clover (*T. pratense* △), winter rye (*S. cereale* ○) and in controls: nutrientsolutions (-) and distilled water (●), at days 0, 2 and 4. Treatments denoted with the same letter (day 4) are not significantly different from each other ($n = 10$, $p < 0.05$) (Friberg et al., 2005)

The experiment progressed in an unprecedented fashion, displaying a significantly higher rate of RS germination in the presence of a non-host perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne*), compared to the susceptible Chinese cabbage (*B. rapa* ssp. *pekensis*) (Suzuki et al., 1992, Rashid et al., 2013). Influence of root activity, measured by sugar concentration and nutrient levels in the exudate was ruled out, implying the presence of a stimuli compound in the exudate. The pursuit of identifying such an germination stimulating factor (GSF) was commenced by a Japanese research group, investigating some fundamental chemical properties of the compound (Suzuki et al., 1992). They found the GSF to express heat stability, slight polarity and a low molecular weight. Conclusively the GSFs were not specific to susceptible plants, and related neither to resistance nor host recognition of *P. brassicae*. In a successive investigating caffeic acid, coumalic acid and corilagin was identified as likely compounds among the GSFs (Ohi et al., 2003).

The GSFs can be divided into two groups relative to their origin: (1) compounds found in host and non-host plant exudates as described above, and (2) compounds unique to the host (Feng et al., 2014). Recently, the presence of a presumably host specific *P. brassicae* enzyme involved in the generation of GSFs was discovered, in an investigation of genes expressed during infection (Feng et al., 2010). The gene Pro1 coding for a serine protease was found highly conserved among the *P. brassicae* pathotypes, and without homologous in other plant pathogens likely to play a unique role in clubroot pathogenesis. In a subsequent experiment, treatment of canola exudates with the identified Pro1 protease verified this hypothesis, demonstrating a significant enhancement of the RS germination (Feng et al., 2010). Presently

the hydrolytes produced by the enzyme activity of Pro1 illustrates a solitary example of the GSFs second group, and could equally serve in the host recognition of *P. brassicae*.

In addition to this, it is reasonable to infer that the stimuli of RS germination extends beyond the GSF compounds, simultaneously influenced and interacting with environmental factors (Feng et al., 2014). Conditions recognised to favour *P. brassicae* include a high humidity, warm temperature, acidic pH and distinct ionic composition of the soil, factors equally influencing the viability of the dormant spore (Macfarlane, 1970, Takahashi, 1994). The role of a spore maturation equivalently has an impact in the initiation of RS germination (Macfarlane, 1970). Conducted studies has demonstrated a substantially higher germination rate of mature RS collected from an old clubroot gall, opposed to immature spores. The spore maturation seemingly coincides with the progressive decay of host tissue, subsequently leading to the dissipation of the spore. This decomposition process is therefore likely to serve as a conditioning, liberating primed spores (Dixon, 2009b).

The germination of *P. brassicae* RS is synchronous, exhibiting a presently unknown mechanism for this differential behaviour (Dixon, 2009b), the use of quorum sensing has been postulated (Björling, 2013). Applying this insight in the trigger mechanism, development of GSF as a biological control agent (BCA), could serve as an effective control method specific for clubroot at this stage, forcing a synchronous germination (Ohi et al., 2003).

Conclusively the intermediate soil survival phase of *P. brassicae* life cycle includes another stage of particular interest. The RS releases a single naked PZ (Hellmers, 1976), exposed to the soil environment only for a transient period of minutes before encystating on a host root hair cell (Tommerup and Ingram, 1971). In this brief moment, the single-walled PZ represents the most vulnerable step of the entire life cycle (Dixon, 2009b), implying a potential for the design of a highly effective control measure of clubroot. Research on this subject is limited, yet modern advances in analytic and cultivation techniques allow an interesting further study.

1.4: Root Hair Infection

An abundance of aspects in the pathogenesis of *P. brassicae* still remains unknown, especially the relative importance of the RHI stage in this context has been a long term puzzle (Feng et al., 2013). It is commonly presumed that the RHI stage serve exclusively to amplify the inoculum of SZ in the soil, oppositely a large density of RS in the soil could compensate for this (Kageyama and Asano, 2009). Generation of PZ under this presumption is questionable, inferring that the RHI stage and PZ must perform an unknown role, necessary in *P. brassicae* life cycle. Elucidation of this subject is therefore the primary objective of this subsection.

The life cycle of *P. brassicae* as previously described and illustrated in figure 1.2 is a simplification of the true events, containing numerous of alternative steps. A Canadian research group addressed such an example, conducting a study on the extent of RHI inflicted by SZ rather than PZ exclusively (Feng et al., 2013). In one of their experiments they investigated the percentage of RHI in a rapeseed cultivar (*Brassica napus* cv. Westar) after inoculation with either RS or SZ as illustrated in figure 1.4 (Feng et al., 2013).

Figure 1.4: Primary infection (a) and secondary infection (b) of canola roots after inoculation with resting spores or secondary zoospores of *Plasmodiophora brassicae* (a) 1×10^4 resting spores mL^{-1} or 1×10^4 secondary zoospores mL^{-1} . (b) 1×10^5 resting spores mL^{-1} or 1×10^4 secondary zoospores mL^{-1} . Means in the plot accompanied by the same letter do not differ based on Fisher's LSD test at $P \leq 0.05$ ($n=10$) (Feng et al., 2013).

In figure 1.4 (b), the SZ inflicts a rapid CI as expected, SZ however inflict a simultaneous RHI of considerable extent as seen in figure 1.4 (a). This observation can be interpreted as a mechanism of *P. brassicae* to insure the presence of a primary infection to some degree. Necessity of an RHI stage is seemingly unambiguous, despite the precise purpose remains to be unveiled. Successive investigation similarly conducted in Canada studied the roles of infection by respectively PZ and SZ in light of previous observations, continuing the pursuit (McDonald et al., 2014). In their experimental design, they selected a rapeseed cultivar (*Brassica napus* cv. Zephyr) for its susceptibility to the *P. brassicae* pathotypes P3 (compatible) and resistance to P6 (incompatible). The primary objective in their experiment was to investigate symptom development under various treatments, of which results can be seen in table 1.4 (McDonald et al., 2014).

Table 1.4: Clubroot severity on harvested roots, area of cortical infection (Area of CI), and number of infected cells with young plasmodia, mature plasmodia or resting spores in five fields of view in sections of canola roots; and mean plant height (cm), shoot weight (g) and root weight (g) of canola "Zephyr", assessed at 52 days after seeding, which was 47 days after inoculation with resting spores (RS) and 42 days after inoculation with secondary zoospores (SZ) of pathotypes 3 and 6 (P3 and P6 respectively) of *Plasmodiophora brassicae*²

Spore type, pathotype	Number of infected cells						Plant growth parameters		
	Incidence (%)	Severity (%)	Area of CI (%)	Young plasmodia	Mature plasmodia	Resting spores	Plant height (cm)	Shoot weight (g)	Root weight (g)
RS-P6	0 a	0 a	0.1 a	22 d	0 a	0 a	49 c	4.0 c	1.1 a
SZ-P6	67 b	31 b	4 b	13 c	6 b	2 b	54 c	4.0 c	1.4 a
SZ-P3	78 c	67 c	12 c	6 b	12 d	12 c	28 b	3.0 b	2.2 b
RS-P6 + SZ-P3	85 c	84 d	18 d	1 a	15 e	26 d	28 b	2.6 b	2.2 b
RS-P3	100 d	100e	33 e	1 a	10 c	32 e	15 a	1.3 a	3.6 c
RS-P3 + SZ-P3	100 d	100 e	34 e	1 a	9 c	32 e	10 a	1.0 a	4.2 c
Control	0	0	0	0	0	0	50 c	4.6 c	1.1 a
Standard error	0.97	1.8	0.40	0.44	0.48	0.60	1.1	0.68	0.97

² Values are the means of eight replications (10 plants per rep for incidence, severity, and plant growth parameters and 1 plant and five fields of view per rep for data on number of infected cells). Means in the columns followed by the same letter do not differ based on Tukey's test at $P \leq 0.05$.

Inoculation of either the compatible or the incompatible RS pathotype presented a different pattern. The avirulent P6-SZ elicited a significantly higher disease severity compared to the P6-RS treatment, and a converse observation could be done on the virulent pathotype P3. Consistent with supplementary observations in their research this indicate a RHI induced suppression of resistance initiation in susceptible cultivars and stimulation of a resistance reaction in resistant cultivars (McDonald et al., 2014). Observation of a significantly higher

disease severity in RS-P6 + SZ-P3 treatment as opposed to the SZ-P3, is nonetheless in controversy with this interpretation. Equivalently, observations of a significantly reduced CI area in RS-P6 + SZ-P3 compared to the RS-P3 + SZ-P6 treatment could be interpreted as an induction of host resistance, primarily residing in the root cortical cells (McDonald et al., 2014). A theory that is consistent with the observations of RHI on resistant and non-host cultivars (Ahmed et al., 2011, Deora et al., 2013).

Injection of the primary plasmodia initiating the RHI stage commence an intricate biochemical defence mechanism referred to as the hypersensitive response (HR) (Agrios, 2005e). The host cell is activated in response to a specific pathogen secreted compound designated as the elicitor, presumed to be the cause of avirulence. In the study of *P. brassicae* mechanism for inducing the suppression of host resistance, the expressed genes of the host cell during an RHI was analysed (McDonald et al., 2014). Numerous of genes involved in the HR defence system was found significantly down-regulated; genes coding for the lignin and salicylic acid biosynthesis as well as the oxidative burst pathway. In addition to this a range of genes involved in pathogen recognition was found up-regulated due to RHI, adding to the importance of the primary stage in the life cycle of *P. brassicae* (McDonald et al., 2014). The discovery of direct CI by PZ is similarly consistent with these observations, indicating that only a lesser RHI is necessary to suppress the host resistance allowing an effective CI (Feng et al., 2013)

Conclusively, the PZ and SZ is morphological indistinguishable as previously mentioned inferring that the differentiated host interaction is most likely due to a difference in the gene expression (Feng et al., 2013). Investigation of this vast task has commenced, studying the genes involved in the pathogenesis of *P. brassicae* (Feng et al., 2012a). The transcriptome and proteome analysis of the clubroot formation is not only a milestone in the study of the intricate host-parasite interaction present in the RHI stage, but decisive in the unveiling of *P. brassicae* pathogenesis (Siemens et al., 2006).

1.5: Cortical Infection

The symptom development of clubroot is primarily caused by the host-parasite interaction occurring in the secondary stage of *P. brassicae* life cycle (Ludwig-Müller et al., 2009). Through the induction of a phytohormone signal cascade, the pathogen manipulates carbon metabolism and several physiological processes of the host. Identification of the particular biochemical pathways essential to this metabolic alteration during pathogenesis, could potentially lead to a determined breeding of more durable resistant cultivars (Diederichsen et al., 2014). Therefore, a vast amount of research has been conducted on this particular field of study, leaving a profound knowledge on the complex mechanism of *P. brassicae* at this stage. A selection on the subject has therefore been a necessity for this subsection, addressing the primary factors in the symptom development (Diederichsen et al., 2014), i.e. the phytohormone classes cytokinin and auxin.

Cytokinins are a significant class of phytohormones influencing numerous of developmental responses, distinguished primarily by their capacity to stimulate cell division (Hopkins and Hüner, 2008f). The root is the major site of cytokinin biosynthesis, supplying the aerial parts through the xylem tissue, where it equivalently stimulate the formation of chloroplast, leaf expansion and shoot differentiation.

In a study of the alteration in carbon metabolism during clubroot disease development, a group of scientists analysed the leaf tissue of a *P. brassicae* infected *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Evans and Scholes, 1995). Throughout the day, leaves of an infected plant was found to contain a significant lower sucrose concentration, and similarly starch storage indicative of either a rapid metabolization or translocation of the photoassimilates (Ludwig-Müller et al., 2009). Successive studies on the differentiated host gene expression during pathogenesis revealed a strong up-regulation in respectively starch synthase and sucrose synthase of infected root cells (Siemens et al., 2006). This consists with observed accumulation of amyloplasts, organelles involved in the starch synthesis and storage (Diederichsen et al., 2014). The extensive manipulation of the host primary metabolism serves to support the parasitic *P. brassicae* with a considerable source of nutrients to thrive on. A step of decisive importance to the pathogen, demonstrated by the effect on an inhibition of a key invertase enzyme which role appears in figure 1.5, visibly reducing the gall growth (Siemens et al., 2011). Conclusively this comprehensive redirection of carbon assimilates in the end leads to a severe retardation of growth in the aerial parts (Ludwig-Müller et al., 2009). The intrinsic mechanism on this phenomenon remains to be elucidated, but may well be associated with the increased concentrations of cytokinin in infected tissues (Siemens et al., 2006). Cytokinins have been found to additionally stimulate the induction of cell wall invertase, hexose transporters and starch synthesis enhancing the metabolic sink, all which are in congruous with the observations (Siemens et al., 2011, Hopkins and Hüner, 2008f).

An intriguing observation revealed that the young secondary plasmodia of *P. brassicae* could synthesise trans-Zeatin (Müller and Hilgenberg, 1986), a common compound of the cytokinins distinguished for its high biological activity (Hopkins and Hüner, 2008f). Secretion of this phytohormone would initiate the signal cascade as seen in figure 1.5 (Diederichsen et al., 2014). The influence of this pathogen derived cytokinin was presumed to constitute a lesser factor in the pathogenicity, due to the detection of a seemingly negligible concentration (Ludwig-Müller et al., 2009). Successively a research group discovered a down-regulation of the genes encoding respectively cytokinin oxidase and dehydrogenase (Siemens et al., 2006), involved in the degradation of the hormone. In coordination with a similar up-regulation in expression of a cytokinin-receptor gene increasing the sensitivity (Siemens et al., 2006), evidence of a cytokinin involvement in the alteration of the hosts primary metabolism seems unambiguous.

As illustrated in figure 1.5, the cytokinin is simultaneously involved in development of root galls, an acute symptom of the clubroot disease. Instigation of hyperplasia is caused by the radical stimulation of cell division, triggering the visual plant overgrowth (Ludwig-Müller et al., 2009).

Figure 1.5: A model for the interaction of roots and leaves in a *Plasmodiophora brassicae*-infected plant, Roots provide the hormonal signals either directly by *P. brassicae* (P.b.) or by induction within the host, which then affect the aboveground plant parts. These in turn provide the roots with nutrients, which are an essential feature for an obligate biotrophic pathogen. Hormones affect and are also affected by primary and secondary metabolies (Diederichsen et al., 2014).

The development of root galls is however not exclusively a product of cytokinin influence as mentioned previously, but instead a coordinated action involving auxin phytohormones (Siemens et al., 2006). Synthesised in the shoot apical meristem and young leaves, this group of compounds participate in the coordination of numerous growth and behavioural processes of pivotal importance to the plant (Lambert et al., 2008). The principal auxin compound is indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) synthesised via the tryptophan or glucosinolate (GSL) pathway, the latter being present in members of Brassicaceae (Hopkins and Hüner, 2008a). Translocation of the hormone is subsequently facilitated by the phloem tissue, despite a considerable amount is involved in a polar transport via the vascular parenchyma cells associated with the xylem.

The auxine hormones take part in a particular plant response of decisive importance to the development of root galls in *P. brassicae* infected root tissue, i.e. stimuli of cell enlargement. This abnormal cell enlargement in the vicinity of xylem cells exert a pressure on the vessel elements, which may be crushed or dislocated reducing the ability to transport water, an event that in severe cases leads to wilting of the aerial parts (Agrios, 2005c).

A few hypothesis have been presented to explain the mechanism underlying the alteration in cell wall extensibility rate causing the enlargement (Evert and Eichhorn, 2012) of which the acid-growth hypothesis is the most commonly accepted. This hypothesis proposes an auxin stimulated excretions of protons to the apoplast, inducing a rapid acidification of the cell wall, causing a structural loosening as depicted in further detail in figure 1.51 (Hopkins and Hüner, 2008a).

Figure 1.51: A schematic demonstrating the role of auxin in the acid-growth hypothesis for cell enlargement. (A) Cell wall polymers (cellulose microfibrils) are extensively cross-linked with load-bearing xyloglycans (1), which limits the capacity of the cell to expand. An auxin-activated ATPase-proton pump located in the plasma membrane acidifies the cell wall space by pumping protons from the cytoplasm. The lower pH activates wall-loosening enzymes, such as extensins, that loosen the load-bearing bonds (2). The forces of turgor acting on the membrane and cell wall cause the polymers to displace (3) and allow the cell to enlarge. (B) A hypothetical signal transduction chain linking auxin with activation of the ATPase-proton pump. Abbreviations: ABP1, auxin-binding protein 1; PLA, phospholipase A₂; FA, fatty acids; LPC, lysophospholipid; PK, protein kinase (Hopkins and Hüner, 2008a).

Binding of the elicitor compound IAA to the membrane-integrated auxin receptor ABP1 initiates the transduction of a signalling cascade, ultimately leading to the activation of a protein kinase (PK) (Hopkins and Hüner, 2008a). Phosphorylation is a key regulatory mechanism of protein activity (Stryer et al., 2011e). The terminal PK catalyses a transfer of a γ-phosphate from ATP in the phosphorylation of ATPase, activating the transporter protein responsible for the proton excretion. Acidification of the apoplast induces an opening of the cell wall directed by two processes (Evert and Eichorn, 2012). (1) Breakage and reformation of non-cellulosic polysaccharides crosslinking the cell wall. (2) Activation of expansin proteins involved in the disruption of hydrogen bonds in polysaccharides, crosslinking the cell wall. The intricate involvement of auxin hormones in the pathogenesis of *P. brassicae* has undergone intensive study in the last decades, enabled by advances in the field of molecular biology (Ludwig-Müller et al., 2009). In a recent investigation of root gall tissue, an immunoreactive response to IAA correlated with the plasmodial development, providing solid evidence for the involvement of auxin hormones (Ludwig-Müller et al., 2009). Compared to the previously cytokinin hormones, no evidence of an auxin biosynthesis pathway in *P. brassicae* has been stated in the available literature. The measured IAA accumulation is therefore presumed to derive exclusively from infected root host cells, induced by the secondary plasmodia (Pasöld et al., 2010). An amplifying factor in this context is the discovered up-regulation of flavonoids synthesis in infected cells, presumably modulating the auxin efflux in root galls as depicted in figure 1.5 (Pasöld et al., 2010). The concrete mechanism underlying this observation is presently unknown, studies however postulate an interaction with the transporters involved in polar transport of auxin (Buer and Muday, 2004). Studies on the genomic expression during the infection of *P. brassicae* have equivalently revealed an up-regulation of the nitrilase genes, indicating that a majority of the accumulated IAA derives from the GSL pathway (Siemens et al., 2006, Ando et al., 2008). These nitrilase

enzymes catalyse the conversion of the intermediate indole-3-acetonitrile (IAN) deriving from GSL in the Brassica family to IAA (Hopkins and Hüner, 2008a). Induction of nitrilase enzymes presumably serves a two-fold effect for the pathogen (Diederichsen et al., 2014), offering a defence mechanism against GSL (Diederichsen et al., 2014, a secondary metabolite involved in the plant defence system (Ludwig-Müller et al., 2009).

Conclusively, studies recently observed an up-regulation of auxine receptors, and through inhibition of these found additional evidence for the importance of the auxine hormones in the establishment of root galls by *P. brassicae* (Jahn et al., 2013).

1.6: Host Range

All members residing in the family of Brassicaceae are acknowledged as potential host plants for *P. brassicae* (Dixon, 2009a). Despite only a few studies have been conducted outside the genera *Brassica*, *Raphanus* and *Arabidopsis* (Hwang et al., 2012a). Commonly cultivated Brassica crops in Denmark includes a number of species in the *Brassica* family, i.e. rapeseed (*B. napus* ssp. *napus*), Turnip (*B. rapa* subsp. *rapa*), cabbage (*B. oleracea* ssp. *capitata*), brusselsprouts (*B. oleracea* ssp. *gemmifera*), broccoli (*B. oleraceae* ssp. *italica*) and borecole (*B. oleraceae* ssp. *acephala*). Equivalently, white mustard (*Sinapis alba*) and oilseed radish (*Raphanus sativus* ssp. *oleiformis*) are important break crops in the Danish agriculture.

A range of common cruciferous weeds (Melander, 2004), including shepherd's purse (*Capsella bursapastoris*), wild mustard (*Sinapsis arvensis*), wild radish (*Raphanus raphanistrum*) and wild turnip (*Brassica campestris*) are similarly hosts to *P. brassicae*, complicating the control of clubroot.

The clubroot disease is commonly presumed to occur solely within species belonging to the Brassicaceae (Ludwig-Müller, 2009). Recent studies on non-host leek (*Allium porrum*) and winter rye (*Secale cereale*) exhibited the potential to stimulate RS germination, and simultaneously exhibited RHI (Friberg et al., 2006). Successive studies on perennial ryegrass not only supported these results, but displayed an CI stage indicating the novel possibility of *P. brassicae* to complete the life cycle on plants previously deemed incompatible (Feng et al., 2012b).

Part 2. Detection and quantification of *Plasmodiophora brassicae* in R&D and development of an on-farm diagnostic kit

P. brassicae is a persistent soil-borne pathogen; infecting a multitude of important crops, common weeds, and equivalently capable of enduring more than 17 years in soil without a host. The aboveground symptoms of an infection are expressed late, and first signs difficult to diagnose due to similarities with symptoms caused by drought, stress or lack of nutrients (Jonsson, 2013). Therefore, a knowledge on the actual infestation level in a given field can be an important management tool to avoid severe yield losses (Burnett et al., 2013), and prevent a further amplification of *P. brassicae* (Jonsson, 2013).

In the following subsections, methods for research & development (R&D) as well as potential tests suited for an on-farm diagnosis will be reviewed.

2.1: Bioassay

The use of a bioassay was the first method developed to investigating the infestation density of *P. brassicae* RS in a soil sample, capable of cultivating the obligate biotroph in vitro (Wakeham, 2015). Despite the development of more advanced molecular biologically based techniques, the bioassay is still applied to validate these methods in scientific experiments (Cao et al., 2007, Li et al., 2013).

The bioassay procedure is described in (Wallenhammar et al., 2011), and essentially involves sowing a chosen plant in a collected soil sample. Depending on the plot size, a given number of subsamples (replicates) are collected from each plot, and thoroughly mixed. In the pooled sample, either a chosen brassica crop or the universally susceptible Chinese cabbage (*B. campestris* ssp. *pekinensis*) is sown. After five or six weeks of growth the root state are visually categorized from 0 to 5, following the description given in table 2.1, and a *disease severity index* (DSI) is calculated.

Table 2.1: Root classification system for calculation of disease severity index (DSI) of Clubroot disease, described in (Wallenhammar et al., 2011)

Class	Symptoms
0	No galls
1	Enlarged lateral roots
2	Enlarged tap root
3	Enlarged napiform tap root
4	Enlarged napiform tap root, lateral roots healthy
5	Enlarged napiform tap root, lateral roots infected

$$DSI = \frac{\sum_{class\ no} [(class\ no.) * (no\ of\ plants\ in\ each\ class)]}{(total\ no.\ of\ plants) * (no.\ of\ classes - 1)} \quad (\text{Wallenhammar et al., 2011})$$

The threshold for symptom development and thereby sensitivity of the bioassay is generally accepted to be 1000 spores g⁻¹ dry soil when using bait plants (Faggian and Strelkov, 2009, Jonsson, 2013).

2.2: Whole Cell Fatty Acid Analysis

The lipid composition of microbial plasma membranes, mitochondria and storage structures is diverse, with more than 300 different fatty acids (Sundelin et al., 2010). An existence of a unique fatty acid composition of each microorganism is the basis for WCFA analysis as a method for detection and quantification. The method proceeds in five-steps, extracting the fatty acids from either plant or *P. brassica* cells (Sasser, 2001). Analysis of the sample is conducted by gas chromatography, and detection of the pathogen achieved by comparing the produced fatty acid profile with a known positive test of *P. brassicae* tissue or database.

Several experiments identifies polyunsaturated Arachidonic acid (20:4 ω 6,9,12,15) (ARA) as a promising biomarker for *P. brassicae* in plant tissue (Sundelin et al., 2010). ARA constitutes an entire 36% of the total fatty acid, and is the single most abundant in *P. brassicae*. Furthermore, ARA is an uncommon component in plant cells, supporting it as a potential biomarker. Observations in a recent experiment is consistent with this theory, demonstrating

an strong correlation between the ARA concentration in a root sample and the soil RS density as illustrated in figure 2.2 (Sundelin et al., 2010).

Figure 2.2: Content of the biomarker fatty acid Arachidonic acid in oilseed rape (cv. Caracas) plants sown in *Plasmodiophora brassicae*-infested soil with increasing soil spore concentration. Measurements were made 35 days after sowing (Sundelin et al., 2010).

The sensitivity of the ARA based WCFA was found to be a 1.6×10^3 RS per g soil as depicted in figure 2.2. Successive discovery of ARA in several soil residing microorganisms limits the method to analysis on plant tissue solely, requiring a time-consuming bioassay. The WCFA analysis is therefore not a potential candidate for on-farm diagnosis of *P. brassicae* RS but instead a valuable analytic method in R&D (Sundelin et al., 2010).

2.3: Real-time Polymerase Chain Reaction

The PCR method relies on the basic principles of replication, and is a common step used to amplify DNA in vitro. Development of gene specific primers corresponding to a target organism extends the application of the method as a sensitive tool for DNA detection. In addition to this, the method can furthermore include the quantification of original DNA in the sample. In Real-time (Rt), also known as quantitative qPCR this is done through an addition of a fluorogenic probe (Stryer et al., 2011c).

After a sufficient amplification, the fluorescence will exceed the background signal defined at the cycle threshold (C_t) point. Quantification is then achieved by a comparison of this extracted C_t value with a known standard, established through Rt-PCR on target DNA samples of known concentration (Stryer et al., 2011c).

Development of gene specific primers for detection and quantification of *P. brassicae* has been an ongoing investigation for more than a decade (Faggian et al., 1999). The present protocol for Rt-PCR analysis demonstrates a detection level of 500 RS per g^{-1} soil (Wallenhammar et al., 2011). Sensitivity of the test is illustrated in figure 2.3, reliable from 1000 to 10^7 RS per g^{-1} soil. The protocol equally demonstrate a strong correlation ($R^2 < 0.99$) between RS density and *P. brassicae* DNA concentration.

Figure 2.3: Linear regression between real-time PCR results (fg plasmid DNA g⁻¹ soil) and number of resting spores of soil X amended with spores of *Plasmodiophora brassicae* in the range 10⁰ – 10⁷ spores g⁻¹ soil. Analysis was performed on two different occasions (squares and diamonds) (n=2) (Wallenhammar et al., 2011).

In the experimental design, they used a *P. brassicae* gene specific TaqMan[®] fluorogenic probe, consisting of a VIC 5'-reporter dye and 3'-Tamrar quencher. A correct primer annealing and elongation leads to the cleavage of the downstream fluorogenic probe catalysed by the exonuclease activity of *Taq* polymerase. This event separates the reporter dye from the quenching, enabling the emission of fluorescent light. A detection demonstrates the presence of *P. brassicae* DNA in the sample, given the assumption that both the probe and primer is highly specific for only the target gene sequence. To ensure that this crucial step is met, both probe and primer is tested in a standard nucleotide *Basic Local Alignment Search Tool* (Blast[®]). Subsequently, several Rt-PCR tests have been conducted on common plant pathogens as a safeguard from eventual false-positives due to an unspecific primer annealing with non-*P. brassicae* DNA.

In the investigation they found a poor correlation between the bioassay derived DSI and resting spores in the soil estimated through Rt-PCR (Wallenhammar et al., 2011). Cause of this contradictory result is likely due to contamination of the bioassay soil, and evidence of a strong correlation has recently been discovered as seen in table 2.31 (Li et al., 2013). Unfortunately the TaqMan[®] probes used in the protocol described by (Wallenhammar et al., 2011) are costly, adding to the expense of the soil analysis (Li et al., 2013). Exchange of the fluorogenic probe to the universally double-strand DNA binding SYBR[®] green reduces the cost, and requires less optimization and pre-reaction preparation (Faggian et al., 2007). The intercalating dye however affects the test sensitivity, increasing the detection threshold to 1000 resting spores g⁻¹ soil (Li et al., 2013). Significance of this loss in detection is on the other hand of lesser importance, since symptom development initiates around a density of 1000 *P. brassicae* RS per g⁻¹ soil, as can be seen on the DSI in table 2.31.

Table 2.31: Results of bioassay for artificially infested soil samples

Number	Spore concentration (number of spores g ⁻¹ soil)	<i>P. brassicae</i> DNA (fg plasmid DNA g ⁻¹ soil)	Disease severity index ¹⁾
1	1.0×10 ⁸	2545	84.85±5.17 a
2	1.0×10 ⁷	2356	78.58±4.92 a
3	1.0×10 ⁶	1876	69.53±2.95 ab
4	1.0×10 ⁵	702	35.67±1.44 c
5	1.0×10 ⁴	265	15.83±4.33 cd
6	1.0×10 ³	40	3.69±3.12 d
7	5.0×10 ²	-	0
8	10	-	0
9	0	-	0

¹⁾ Different letters indicate statistically significant difference within each sample ($P < 0.05$). (Li et al., 2013)

The current commercial test available for Danish farmers is based on this novel Rt-PCR protocol, and conducted by Eurofins Steins laboratory A/S. Expected processing time from the arrival of a soil sample is generally 1-2 weeks, costing 2500 DKK each, providing a quantity discount for larger orders. Due to protection of the specific analytic protocol, the applied type of fluorogenic probe remains unknown. An alteration in the probe would nevertheless reduce the cost to a minor degree (Li et al., 2013), since the main expense of the analytic procedure is paid labour hours (Faggian et al., 2007). The specified time expectancy for the test results is currently perplexingly long, as the analysis itself requires less than one working day to be performed (Wallenhammar et al., 2011). Majority of the time is spend transporting the soil samples to Eurofins Steins department in Sweden (Nielsen, 2011), and a future independent test in Denmark could likely reduce both processing time and cost. An advisory interpretation of the test results is given for the farmer as illustrated in table 2.32 (Nielsen, 2011).

Table 2.32 (English translation). Advisory interpretation of RT-PCR results on *P. brassica* infested soil, after (Nielsen, 2011)

No. DNA copies (g ⁻¹ soil)	Amount of Plasmid DNA (g ⁻¹ soil)	Advisory Interpretation
No <i>P. brassicae</i> DNA detected in sample	-	Infestation is not documented, low risk of an attack
< 1300	< 5 fg	There is a risk of less than 10% yield loss There is a risk of further amplification of <i>P. brassicae</i> if susceptible brassica crops are cultivated.
1300 – 50.000	5 – 200 fg	There is a risk of more than an 10% yield loss There is a risk of a further amplification of <i>P. brassicae</i> if susceptible brassica crops are cultivated
> 50.000	> 200 fg	Cultivation of susceptible brassica crops is not recommended due to risk of high yield losses.

The Rt-PCR test is a solid method, capable of achieving a sensitive detection and quantification of *P. brassicae* in both soil and plant tissue. Through the application of specific primers in the Rt-PCR analysis, the method similarly allows a theoretical detection of *P. brassicae* pathotypes in the sample. Development of such primers has however not yet been successful (Personal communication, SLU 2015) with one possible exception. In a recently published report, they found primers to a gene *Cr811* involved in clubroot pathogenesis as specific for pathotype 5 of the European Clubroot Differentials (ECD) (Zhang et al., 2015). Detection of pathotypes through this method, would enable a further unveiling of *P. brassicae*'s complex behaviour, and possibly contribute to the control of clubroot.

Already commercially available, the method has a growing potential as a tool for farm management in the control of clubroot disease. However, it is of paramount importance that a Danish test is established in near future, in order to promote implementation of the test. An optimisation of DNA extraction to overcome the basic complications such as soil acidity and soil-DNA interactions is an equally important aspect for future improvement of this method (Faggian et al., 2007).

2.4: Enzyme-linked Immunosorbent Assay

In parallel to the development of a DNA based Rt-PCR analysis, researchers studied the application of serological tests as a diagnostic tool. These tests utilize the antibodies property of high affinity binding to specific antigens (Faggian et al., 2007). Common to all mammalian immune systems, the antibodies act as a line of defence against foreign organisms or substrates. Among the broad spectrum of different serological tests, several studies found that an indirect plate trapped antigen (PTA) enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) exhibited the greatest diagnostic potential (Faggian et al., 2007, Wakeham and White, 1996). The basic principles of this technique is a coating of microtiter wells with antigens, i.e. eventual *P. brassicae* RS of a sample (Stryer et al., 2011a). Addition of primary antibodies then binds specifically to the antigens. A secondary anti-specie antibody, conjugated to alkaline phosphatase is then added, binding to the previously applied primary antibody. Cleavage of the chromogenic substrate p-nitrophenylphosphate catalysed by the linked-enzyme demonstrates the positive presence of the antigen, hence *P. brassicae* spore in the sample. Furthermore, the rate of colour formation measured at 405 nm, is proportional to the original amount of antigen and thus enables a quantification of the sample (Stryer et al., 2011a) Previous studies applied polyclonal antibodies deriving from different β -cells (Wakeham and White, 1996), being incapable of reproduction this strongly limited the test as a diagnostic tool. Recent studies however successfully manufactured monoclonal antibodies (mABs), specific for *P. brassicae*, demonstrating virtually no cross-reactivity with a range of tested non-obligate pathogens (Faggian et al., 2007). Investigation of the detection threshold using these mABs in an indirect ELISA was not given in the published paper, it is however often higher than the PCR method and hence less sensitive.

Development of *P. brassicae* mABs has brought the serological tests to a new level, applying indirect ELISA as a method for both screening and cross reactivity analysis. These low cost mABs show a promising potential as a near future candidate for an on-farm diagnostic test.

2.5: On-farm Diagnostic Test

As previously mentioned an effective control of *P. brassicae* is likely to depend foremost on a successful diagnostic of the infestation level in the field. Development of an on-farm test available for Danish farmers is therefore of decisive importance. A broad range of factors determines the degree of how well this test will integrate as a tool in farm management (Faggian et al., 2007). Firstly, the farmer should be able to perform the test independently and interpretation of the results unambiguous. Secondly, application of the test must be cost-efficient, implying an economical gain in the usage. Thirdly, quick but infallible and without subject to neither false negatives nor positives. Lastly, semi-quantitative allowing an evaluation of the infestation level and eventual control progression.

A collaboration between forensic departments in UK and Australia led to the publication of such an on-farm diagnostic kit in 2007, based on a mAB loaded lateral flow device (LFD) (Faggian et al., 2007). This test is established on a well-known platform, similarly employed in the home pregnancy strips.

Analysis of a soil or water sample is performed through application upon the LFD conjugation pad as seen in figure 2.5 (Kennedy et al., 2013). Any present *P. brassicae* RS, hence antigens bind at this step to highly specific gold-labelled mABs. By capillary action, the mAB-antigen complex travels through the membrane pad, binding to specific ABs at the test line. Single, excess mABs however continues until binding to secondary ABs at the control line, validating a successful test run.

Figure 2.5 Lateral flow strip construction (Kennedy et al., 2013)

With a minor time expenditure of less than 10 minutes, this test provides not only a rapid but equally a cheap method for detection of *P. brassicae* at only 50 DKK per strip (Wakeham, 2015).

The test similarly meets the requirements of the semi-quantitative property, exhibiting a test line colorization proportional to the density of *P. brassicae* spores in the sample. Interpretation of this test line nevertheless implies an undesirable degree of subjectivity, involving the necessity of a hand held lateral flow reader for an accurate analysis (Faggian et al., 2007). However, the test distributors is likely to propose a package deal including such a reader, in interest of promoting the application of the method.

The detection threshold of the mAB-based test is 10^5 spores per gram soil, justifying that this only delivers a positive detection in field infestation levels of economic importance to the farmer (Faggian et al., 2007). Whether this test limit is acceptable for Danish farmers is on the

other hand questionable. As can be seen in table 2.32, a field of such an infestation level would be affected by severe yield losses, and placed well above advisory limits for cultivation of any susceptible crops (Nielsen, 2011).

In addition to cross-reactivity test of the applied mABs, recent studies found a successful detection of six *P. brassicae* pathotypes using the LFD (Kennedy et al., 2013), providing strong evidence for the test credibility.

Development of a LFD based on-farm diagnostic kit for *P. brassicae* shows promising potential as a near-future tool for Danish farmers. Implementation of a 50 DKK test strip as a partial replacement of the current Rt-PCR costing 2500 DKK per sample will likely play a significant role in the control of clubroot. Future optimization regarding the soil-inhibitors is decisive to increase the sensitivity and equally eliminate risks of false negatives (Wakeham, 2015). The issuing of a premature commercial test will have detrimental effect on the near-future implementation of such an on-farm diagnostic kit, emphasizing the importance of an infallible test (Faggian et al., 2007).

2.6: Sampling

The infestation of the soil-borne pathogen *P. brassicae* is often distributed in patches through the field, implying necessity for a consistent and thoroughly sampling (Cao et al., 2007). Usage of a common standardized method extracting subsamples in a “W” pattern is commonly accepted as the most adequate technique (Jonsson, 2013). Additional subsampling should be collected from the field gate, moist areas or areas of lower pH where the pathogen thrives (Nielsen, 2011). Depending on the infestation level up to 40 subsamples per ha is recommended, these are thoroughly mixed to a pooled sample and shipped for analysis. A slight drawback to this procedure is the risks of a false negative, due to a possible dilution of a positive subsamples (Faggian et al., 2007), the method will nonetheless give a general impression of the field infestation level.

2.7: Infestation Mapping

The development of precise methods for detection and quantification of *P. brassicae* enables field mapping of infestation level as a tool for farm management. Localization of the infested patches allows a targeted application of the chosen control methods, length of crop rotation or cultivation practices (Jonsson, 2013). Design of a field survey is described in (Wallenhammar et al., 2011). In this investigation an extraction of 30 subsamples in a 3-meter radius was conducted, and pool to a uniform sample. Each subsample had its location GPS-tagged and run through an Rt-PCR analysis for quantification of *P. brassicae*. Results of the survey is illustrated in figure 2.7 (Wallenhammar et al., 2011).

Implementation of such an infestation map has a set of complications whereas the cost-efficiency is of primary concern. The large-scale measurement requires up to 40 soil samples tested per ha, an investment that under current circumstances would be deemed highly economically unsustainable. Prospective for using GPS in the future, as a tool in farm management is uncertain, a geographic information system (GIS) might instead serve as a visualization tool of disease development for legislative decisions on a national scale.

Figure 2.7: Probability of detecting > 5 fg plasmid DNA of *Plasmodiophora brassicae* g⁻¹ in soil samples estimated by indicator kringing in field at farm 2. The distribution of the measured values (n=40) is displayed as black dots (Wallenhammar et al., 2011).

Part 3. Control of clubroot disease.

The symptoms of clubroot disease is as previously mentioned, formation of distinct root galls, yellowing of leaves, retardation of growth and eventual wilting of the aerial parts. Severity of the disease in a given field, is determined by the sum of an interaction between three primary components, often visualized as an triangle depicted in the figure 3 (Agrios, 2005a).

Figure 3: The disease triangle (Agrios, 2005a)

Elimination of a single component in this triangle; a susceptible host, virulent pathogen, or favourable environment, will create a setting where disease cannot occur (Schumann and D'Arcy, 2006a). In the case of clubroot disease, the present approach is comprised of several methods directed at each of these components. Commonly this involves an implementation of resistant lines, a dynamic crop rotation and utilization of soil amendments, i.e. liming and drainage.

Clubroot is far from a novel disease in the cultivation of WR in Danish agriculture, and despite an immense knowledge, the issue is of inclining concern. Hereby not stated that the previous

cited methods are inefficient, a correct application exploiting the cooperative action of several methods can achieve a reasonable control. Revision of the current management strategy is necessary, in order to efficiently address the escalating spread.

Initially, an improved distribution of knowledge obtained in R&D to the advisory companies is required, this step ensure the farmers a modernized management strategy. Incorrect farm practices in e.g. the absence of an efficient field-machinery sanitation constituted a substantial source to the spread of clubroot (Nielsen, 2015), an issue that needs to be addressed. Additional contamination sources include; wind and water dissipation, vectors and even animal manure, since environmental resistant RS can traverse the digestive system without an substantial effect in its vitality (Dixon, 2009b, Hobolth, 1977).

Introduction of a later sowing date of WR could equally be an control measure to avoid an early infection of *P. brassicae* in warm and moist autumns (Burnett et al., 2013). A variety of environmental parameters dictates the cause of clubroot disease development, of which temperature is a major influent in e.g. resting spore germination, and root gall development (Gossen et al., 2013, Sharma et al., 2011a). As a closure on this subject, a later sowing date is however commonly associated with a lower seed yield (Hwang et al., 2012b), emphasizing caution in applying this practice.

The economical aspect is an unavoidable part of the farmers decision-making process, demanding an economical benefit from the application of a control method. The estimated income for WR crops in Denmark (2015), lies relative to the yield between 1979 and 4148 DKK per ha, incl. man-hours spend in the process (Personal communication, LandboNord 2015). The economic leeway in one-season for implementing a control method is therefore marginal, when taking an account of the additional expenses in e.g. fuel and man-hours to apply the practice. A management strategy should therefore be considered a long-term investment, preventing a further escalation of the issue.

The following subsections will address the present control methods, i.e. resistant lines, crop rotation and soil amendments in further detail, reviewing the current status of each.

3.1: Resistant Cultivars

Deployment of genetic resistant rapeseed cultivars is the leading strategy in the management of clubroot disease in Denmark (Personal communication, LandboNord 2015), introduced to the market in 2001 (Jensen, 2014, Diederichsen et al., 2014). Integration of this control method is practically undemanding, and supported by numerous studies in its indisputable reduction of yield losses compared to susceptible cultivars on infested soil (Burnett et al., 2013, Peng et al., 2014d). The resistant cultivars commercially available to Danish farmers comprise of only a handful, of which the most prominent includes Mendel, Mentor, Mendelson, SY Alister and Andromeda.

In Denmark a range of crop cultivars are evaluated in national trials (Landsforsøgene), to ensure advisory companies the necessary information to guide farmers in the selection of a cultivar. In these trials only the resistant cultivars Mendelson, and Mentor are presently being evaluated, the latter of which demonstrated a promising relative yield of 101, producing an average of 5435 kg seeds per ha (Sortinfo, 2015). Despite a reasonable performance, a significant yield difference still exist relative to highly productive susceptible cultivars such as

Quartz, demonstrating a relative yield of 108 (Sortinfo, 2015). Therefore the deployment of a resistant cultivar is only economically justified in moderately infested fields, i.e. a minor development of clubroot disease in the Quartz cultivar might not inflict noteworthy yield losses. Equivalently, use of the resistant cultivars is discouraged unless a moderate infestation is detected to prolong the resistance durability until novel cultivars are available (Personal communication, SEGES 2015).

In a recent trial, four resistant WR cultivars and the susceptible DK Explicit was grown on a severely clubroot infested field located in the northern Jutland from 2013 to 2014, yields are illustrated in figure 3.12 (NFTS, 2014).

Preliminary results

Landsforsøgene®

Figure 3.12

Yield of winter rapeseed cultivars on severely clubroot infested field (P03), Denmark 2013 - 2014. Means with dissimilar letters are significantly different. DM, Dry matter (NFTS, 2014).

It is important to emphasize that the results of this trial is preliminary and interpretation should be done with reservations. Evident observation can nonetheless be inferred; seed yield of the susceptible cultivar DK Explicit is significantly reduce as expected, compared to the resistant. The impact of clubroot disease in the severely infested field is not completely controlled by the resistant cultivars, e.g. Mentor, is inflicted by a substantial yield loss of more than 2 tons relative to the yield potential mentioned earlier (Sortinfo, 2015). The cultivar Mendelson exhibiting a relatively good performance in this trial, and is presently being introduced to the Swedish WR production, replacing Mendel (Wallenhammar et al., 2014). In Germany, each of the four cultivars in the trial is represented with a prevalence of Mentor in 2015 (Personal communication, NPZ 2015). A thorough evaluation of Mendelson, Andromeda and SY Alister cultivar in the Danish national trials would be interesting.

The four resistant cultivars perform in a uniform fashion in response to clubroot, indicative of their common decent from Mendel. This parentage is an issue of mounting concern, since the cultivars contain the same clubroot resistant (CR) gene(s) (Personal communication, JKI Germany 2015). If a novel virulent pathotype emerges, capable of inflicting clubroot symptoms in a previously deemed resistant cultivar, then the remaining cultivars are equally susceptible (Nielsen, 2015). In an extensive project carried out by HGCA in UK, observations of incomplete control in the Mendel cultivar was interpreted as indicative of the exerted pressure on the CR gene (Burnett et al., 2013). This theory is consistent with the incomplete control of resistant cultivars observed in figure 3.12. Development of cultivars with novel CR

genes is therefore decisive to retain this control method in the future. The breeding programs addressing this matter are highly intricate and despite the pivotal role, only a brief outline of the field will be presented.

Rapeseed (*B. napus*) is an artificial species of comparatively recent origin and derives from the hybridization of parental species *B. rapa* and *B. oleracea* as illustrated in figure 3.13 (Warwick, 2011).

Figure 3.13: Triangle of U, showing the genetic relationship among the six cultivated species of *Brassica*. Adapted from U (1935) (Warwick, 2011)

Through backcrossing of ancestral species, the breeding process is capable to utilize a large CR gene pool in the pursuit of novel sustainable resistant cultivars (Peng et al., 2014a). The dominant gene inducing the primary resistance response in Mendel originates from *B. rapa* (cultivar ECD-04)(Diederichsen and Sacristan, 1996), a specie that has been found to contain several promising CR genes for future breeding (Peng et al., 2014a). In order to exploit this resource, breeding efficiency needs to be substantially improved since two out of three CR genes were lost in the process of developing Mendel (Diederichsen et al., 2006). Introduction of marker assisted selection (MAS) has solved this issue, enabling an identification of plants expressing the particular CR genes in the breeding process (Joshi and Sanghamitra, 2010). In collaboration with an assessment and characterization of available CR genes, these techniques enables an efficient breeding of novel resistant cultivars (Rahman et al., 2014).

The importance of resistance breeding is inclining in parallel with the production of WR crops, and a range of large international breeding companies, i.e. NPZ, Limagrain and Syngenta are involved. Introduction of novel cultivars is therefore anticipated to occur in near future (Personal communication, JKI 2015). Furthermore, trials are currently being conducted in Sweden and Germany to elucidate the resistance durability of present and advancing breeding lines (Wallenhammar et al., 2014).

3.1.2: *P. brassicae* Pathotypes

The CR genes incorporated in the resistant cultivars have been found to exhibit a pathotype specific response (Diederichsen et al., 2009). To uniform the characterization of *P. brassicae* pathotypes the ECD (Buczacki et al., 1975) and Williams (Williams, 1966) set was developed. These sets categorized the pathotypes relative to their differentiated host virulence.

In Germany, the Julius Kühn-institute has conducted comprehensive studies on the subject of differentiated resistance response of rapeseed cultivars against various *P. brassica* pathotypes. In their study, they mapped the prevalent distribution of pathotypes, as illustrated in figure 3.14 (Zamani, 2014).

Figure 3.14: Distribution of the *Plasmodiophora* pathotypes in Germany. (2013 – 2014; n = 40) (Zamani, 2014)

The cultivation of WR in northern Germany is severely inflicted by clubroot disease (Strehlow et al., 2014), evidently caused by the dominant P1. Pathotypes not displayed with an (+) are commonly accepted to cause less than 30% disease severity in the available resistant cultivars (Personal communication, JKI 2015). The frequency of P1 pathotype in the northern Germany consist with the few observations made on Danish soil, equally demonstrating a prevalence of P1 in Aarup, Flemming and Vojens, and P1+ in Middelfart (Lüders et al., 2011, Zamani, 2014). Detection of a P1+ pathotype recognized to exhibit virulence on the present resistance cultivars in Denmark, is a likely threat to the WR cultivation. Efforts in mapping the pathotype prevalence in Denmark should therefore be encouraged to elucidate the extent of this threat. Furthermore, this observation equally supports the necessity of introducing novel CR genes in resistant cultivars, able to fend of this new generation of virulent pathotypes.

The mapping of pathotype prevalence could correspondingly serve as a future tool in the farmers selection of a resistant cultivar, exhibiting pathotype specific mechanisms. Concurrently, studies in a novel breeding technique, gene-pyramiding show promising advances in the development of durable resistance against multiple pathotypes, employing the molecular assisted selection procedure (Joshi and Sanghamitra, 2010, Matsumoto et al., 2012).

A further elucidation of the mechanism underlying host-parasite interaction, leading to the development of clubroot and erosion of resistance could equally contribute to an efficiently targeted breeding, emphasizing further study on the subject (Hwang et al., 2011a).

Conclusively, the deployment of resistant cultivars should be done in cooperation with appropriate cultural practices, e.g. crop rotation and soil amendments to ensure a correct management of clubroot (Peng et al., 2014a), e.g. application of various WR cultivars with dissimilar CR genes in the crop rotation could substantially improve the control efficiency and resistance durability in near future against multiple pathotypes (Rahman et al., 2014). As a last remark, deployment of resistant cultivars is a long-term management strategy due to longevity of resting spores, persisting for more than 17 years in the soil (Wallenhammar, 1996).

3.2: Crop Rotation

In the management of pest, crop rotation is presumably the first control measure employed in the European agriculture, dating back to the middle-ages (Bruns, 2012). Integration of diverse crops in the rotation remains a key management strategy to disrupt the pathogens life-cycle, forcing a stage of starvation by removing the susceptible host “component”, as previously illustrated in figure 3 (Schumann and D’Arcy, 2006b). This sanitary measure is however less efficient in the control of soil inhabitants such as *P. brassicae* due to the longevity of its RS (Agrios, 2005f). Application of a crop rotation is nonetheless a common control practice, simultaneously contributing to the soil fertility through incorporation of e.g. organic matter and nitrogenous compounds (Wallenhammar et al., 2014).

The design of a crop rotation is highly influenced by economy, and farmers often tend to specialize in a few crops of high net return in short rotations (Cook, 2006). These unsustainable crop systems are exposed to developing severe issues of clubroot disease, and presumably the main cause behind the occurring aggravation (Hwang et al., 2014, Wallenhammar et al., 2014). In addition to this, short crop rotations with resistant cultivars increase the exerted pressure on the frail CR genes, accelerating the breakdown of resistance (Rahman et al., 2014).

Few studies have dealt with the subject of crop rotation as a control practice concerning club disease in recent years. This includes an extensive Swedish investigation conducted from 1969 to 1992, which examined the influence of crop rotation and edaphic factors on the development of clubroot disease in severely infested fields (Wallenhammar, 1996). A key observation in this field survey were the direct relationship between infestation level and length of crop rotation, i.e. number of oilseed crops grown in the time span 1969 to 1985, as illustrated in figure 3.2. The infestation level was assessed in a bioassay technique, described previously.

The four cropping intensities of oilseed rape illustrated in the figure 3.2 correspond to an approximate crop rotation of 1 in 3, 4, 5 and 8 years, respectively. An evident observation is the infestation level at outset of the survey in 1986, significantly lower in longer intervals between oilseed crops in the rotation. This pattern is however not visible in the final infestation level measured, without a significant different from the short 1 in 3 as opposed to the long 1 in 8 crop rotation. An underlying factor causing this controversy could be the asynchronous germination of dormant RS. In addition to this, a systematic (significant) decrease is observed from 1990 to 1992 in all fields according to the bioassay, indicative of an escalating decrease in virulence after an approximate 7 years without a susceptible host. Despite the peculiarity of several aspects in the observations, none of these were discussed in the paper (Wallenhammar, 1996).

Figure 3.2: Relationship between the percentage of diseased plants in the bioassay and oilseed rape cropping intensity. Letters over the bars show significance according to Duncan's multiple range test, $P > 0.05$. (Wallenhammar, 1996)

Crop rotations of WR in Denmark is commonly 1 in 5 years, a cultivation instruction given by SEGES, Knowledge Center for Agriculture (SEGES, 2015)(Personal communication, LandboNord 2015). In the Swedish field survey, an long-term assessment of infestation level was assessed in a single field using bio-assays, and results were successively correlated with years since the last susceptible oilseed crop, illustrated in figure 3.21 (Wallenhammar, 1996). The decline of disease incidence in a field with a well-established *P. brassicae* RS density is slow, reaching subclinical levels after an approximate 17 years. According to this model, a crop rotation of 1 WR in 5 years would decrease the incidence level from 72% to 44%. Despite a substantial reduction, this crop rotation length is likely to be inadequate against severely infested fields. Designing an efficient crop rotation in this case might e.g. implicate an extension of the interval length to 1 in 8 or 1 in 9, an approach recommended by SEGES (SEGES, 2015). Instead, an analysis of the soils properties and infestation level could guide a more precise selection of rotation length at the individual field. The rotation length is nonetheless irrelevant if an inefficient weed control allow *P. brassicae* to proliferate on susceptible weeds, or improper sanitation allow transport of infested soil from other fields (Wallenhammar, 1996).

Figure 3.21: *Plasmodiophora brassicae* in spring oilseed rape. Percentage of diseased plants in the bioassay correlated with time passed since the last oilseed crop was grown in the field investigated. (Wallenhammar, 1996)

The Danish farmers is according to the legislation imposed to cultivate a minimum 10% of their total arable land as break crops yearly (NaturErhvervstyrelsen, 2014). This infers an additional risk of amplifying the spread since the susceptible white mustard (*Sinapis alba*) and oilseed radish (*Raphanus sativus ssp. oleiformis*) are both important break crops in Denmark.

In addition to this, another major challenge ahead is the new 2015 environmental focus (MFO) crop legislation (Personal communication, LandboNord), imposing a number of specific directions the farmer must pass to obtain a 1/3 of his EU financial support. In short, a minimum 5% of the farmers total arable land must be cultivated accordingly with MFO crops, i.e. environmental sustainable land around relics and lakes, fallow, buffer zones along streams and coppices. Deployment of MFO break crops is similarly an option, composed of a pure grass, grass and clover or mixtures of dicot break crops, e.g. oilseed radish and white mustard of the Brassicaceae family. These MFO break crops count with a conversion factor of 0.3, i.e. 1 ha of an oilseed radish and white mustard mixture equals 0.3 ha, adding the mandatory break crops discussed previously in the calculation. Conclusively the farmers are situated in a difficult position, having to design an intricate crop rotation in order to avoid unintentionally aggravating the incidence of clubroot disease. The advisory guide issued by SEGES however state that cultivation of oilseed radish amplify the disease incidence in a minor degree, and should therefore be preferred relative to white mustard if necessary (SEGES, 2015).

Finally, a crop rotation of 1 in 5 should be retained as a precautionary measure in the Danish WR production. Effectivity of this practice implies a correct design, i.e. avoiding the cultivation of susceptible hosts as break crops and an equally effective weed control. Are these requirements met, a crop rotation can in conjunction with resistant cultivars obtain an substantial control of clubroot disease (Peng et al., 2014d).

3.3: Soil Amendment

The development and persistence of clubroot disease is well recognized to be influenced by edaphic factors i.e. physical and chemical properties of the soil (Donald and Porter, 2009). Fundamental properties such as soil type, organic matter and clay content was found to significantly influence the level of infestation in a field, illustrate in figure 3.3 (Wallenhammar, 1996).

Figure 3.3: Relationship between the percentage of diseased plants in the bioassay and different soil conditions. (A) Correlation with soil types. (B) Correlation with organic matter. (C) Correlation with clay content. Letters over the bars show significance according to Duncan's multiple range test, $P < 0.05$. (Wallenhammar, 1996)

According to this model, a clay soil type would substantially promote the infestation level, alongside low organic matter content. The majority of Danish soils are either coarse or fine sand as illustrated in table 3 (Ipsen et al., 2011), a beneficial feature that might limit the *P. brassicae* pathogen in some degree.

Table 3: Danish soil type categorization & national distribution. After (Ipsen et al., 2011)

JB no.		Fraction of Danish soil (%)
1-3	Coarse sand	41
4-6	Fine sand	45
7-9	Clay	7
10-12	Silt	7

A number of edaphic factors are likely to interact with *P. brassicae*. In the following subsections the cultural practices of drainage, liming and boron amendment will be reviewed as control methods against clubroot disease.

3.3.1: Drainage

The use of drainage is a common water management strategy to minimize the risk of crop-water stress, capable of causing substantial yield reductions (Hollinger and Angel, 2009c). Furthermore, a number of additional benefits are associated with a well-drained field, e.g. enhanced soil structure and resistance to soil compaction allowing a timelier field operation. An implementation of drainage does however require a precaution regarding the risk of water deficiency in the decisive flowering season of WR from mid-April to the end of May (Ipsen et

al., 2011). The use of irrigation might therefore be necessary to compensate the insufficient precipitation. At present an estimated half of the arable land in Denmark is therefore being drained (Hansen, 2012).

Drainage is acknowledged as a precautionary management strategy to control clubroot disease, limiting a decisive factor; soil moisture, facilitating the dissipation of the pathogen (Burnett et al., 2013). The PZ and SZ of *P. brassicae* are both biflagellate, a feature that enables an effective exploitation of the soil in the pursuit of a susceptible host (Dixon, 2009b). Despite this locomotive action the stages are short lived, only permitting the zoospores to traverse a short distance in this vulnerable stage (Hobolth, 1977). The mechanism of drainage is therefore to remove excess water; limiting the ability of *P. brassicae* zoospores to seek a susceptible host. In studies conducted nearly a century ago, a moisture content of 60% and higher of the fields water holding capacity was found to increase clubroot severity (Monteith, 1924). High disease severity has nonetheless been observed during dry seasons, presumably reflecting the reduced functionality of infected plants root system, rendering the foliage susceptible to water stress (Agrios, 2005c, Dixon, 2009b).

The increased necessity to irrigate WR crops is likely to intensify proliferation of *P. brassicae*, escalating this risk is the simultaneous high temperature often observed under such circumstances (Hobolth, 1977). Drainage is equally associated with an higher soil temperature (Hollinger and Angel, 2009c), found to increase both RS germination and disease severity (Sharma et al., 2011a, Sharma et al., 2011c).

Literature on drainage as a control method is limited, and dates back to the early 20th century, nonetheless it is a commonly recognized management strategy against clubroot disease in Denmark (SEGES, 2015, Hobolth, 1977). The removal of areas prone to waterlogging could therefore serve as an approach to limit the patchy distribution of *P. brassicae*, facilitating an effective control of clubroot disease.

The drainage of fields is an large investment of 10-20.000 DKK per ha, especially in a time of economic uncertainty in the Danish agriculture (Hansen, 2012). Applying this management strategy exclusively due to an observed clubroot incidence is therefore unlikely, but a factor of decisive importance (Personal communication, Gefion 2015).

3.3.2: Liming & Boron Amendment

Liming of clubroot infected fields has been a control measure long before the causative agent *P. brassicae* was classified in 1878 (Anderson, 1855) cited in (Dixon, 2009b), and still remains one of the principal control means (Burnett et al., 2013). The pH value of soil is a decisive chemical attribute influencing on e.g. nutrient availability and activity of the microbial community (Hollinger and Angel, 2009a). Therefore, a pH of arable land is commonly maintained in the interval of 6.0 to 6.5, optimum for crop productivity. Liming of soils is an efficient technique to adjust the soil pH, conducted through extensive tillage of the field, ensuring a uniform incorporation of the particles. The ability of a liming product to rise the pH is defined by its effective neutralizing value hence quality, determined from the fineness of grind and calcium carbonate equivalent (Hollinger and Angel, 2009a). Successively, the effectivity of liming as a control practice is influenced by a number of variables, i.e. particle distribution, quality, soil properties and interval between application and planting (Donald and Porter, 2009).

Numerous investigations has dealt with this subject, including a particular extensive project recently conducted by the HGCA division in UK, on the basis of six field trials between 2007 and 2010 (Burnett et al., 2013). A key result of their investigation was the observation of a strong correlation between soil pH and clubroot severity as illustrated in figure 3.3.2.

Figure 3.3.2: The correlation between clubroot severity and soil pH in the spring assessments at the Herefordshire 2008/2009 site (Burnett et al., 2013).

Evident figure 3.3.2, the disease severity declines substantially at a pH around 7.0 consistent with a preceding study that concluded a pH of 7.2 and inclining would be optimal for the management of clubroot (Hwang et al., 2011b, Gossen et al., 2013). Conclusively, an application of calcium carbonate at 8 tons per ha exhibited the highest mean control on 25% in the project. Enhancement of soil pH should nonetheless be done with caution of manganese deficiency, (SEGES, 2002).

The mechanism of action in liming has been suggested to interfere with a number of decisive elements in *P. brassicae* lifecycle such as the RS germination, zoospore motility, RHI and CI (Dixon, 2009b). In a recently conducted investigation, the effect of an inclining alkaline pH was found to reduce RS germination substantially, as illustrated in figure 3.3.21 (Rashid et al., 2013). Equivalently, the RHI frequency was simultaneously reduced at alkaline conditions impeding the establishment of *P. brassicae*, an event that might explain the observed decline in clubroot severity. The influence on RHI was however not observed in the absence of calcium salts, supporting a differentiated effect of liming, respectively due to pH and calcium concentration individually (Webster and Dixon, 1991). Uptake of calcium is recognized to enhance cell-wall stiffening by binding to pectin components (Lambert et al., 2008), providing a mechanical protection against infection. In addition to this, proton abundant environments have been postulated to exert an antagonistic effect on the calcium absorption (Dixon, 2009b), a theory that is consistent with the inclining RHI frequency observed at acidic pH (Rashid et al., 2013).

Figure 3.3.21: Effect of a wide-range of pH values on *Plasmidiophora brassicae* resting spores germination. The resting spores were incubated at 25° with nutrient solution (B). Germination was recorded as a function of length incubation in days (DAT, days after treatment) over 6 days. Data represent the means of 3 replicates from two combined trials. The bars indicate the standard errors (Rashid et al., 2013).

In controversy with this observation, a parallel study conducted on 267 infested fields found a weak correlation between soil pH and clubroot severity (Gossen et al., 2013). Instead, the study observed an evident interaction between soil pH and temperature as illustrated in figure 3.3.22.

Figure 3.3.22: The effect of temperature and pH on clubroot severity in canola inoculated with *Plasmidiophora brassicae* under controlled conditions (Gossen et al., 2013).

Optimal conditions for *P. brassicae* were found at a temperature of 20 to 25°C, and pH 5 to 6. The study provided evidence that despite unfavourable alkaline pH well above optimum, moderate levels of clubroot could develop when temperature and moisture were suitable (Gossen et al., 2013).

Conclusively, the practice of liming demonstrates a potential in reducing clubroot severity, presumably interfering with RS germination and colonization of *P. brassicae*. Usage of liming practices is nonetheless rare in Danish WR cultivation, despite it is commonly applied as a control measure in the cultivation of cruciferous vegetables (Personal communication, SEGES 2015). In the cited studies, prohibitively large amounts was applied to achieve a substantial

control, requiring time-consuming incorporation, fuel expenditure and man-hours (Hwang et al., 2011b). An integration of a liming practice is therefore a long-term investment, establishing and maintaining a pH around 7.2.

An additional soil amendment boron was put on trial in the HGCA project (Burnett et al., 2013). This compound has been suggested to effect the ability of *P. brassicae* zoospores to colonize a host plant (Dixon, 2009b). In the project application of 20 kg per ha of soluble boron was found to have a predicted mean control of 18%, equally lifting the yield by a mean of 12% (Burnett et al., 2013). An eventual phytotoxic effect of boron has been a concern, studies nonetheless found no significant pattern in yield reduction nor risk of negative effects on crops in the rotation at application rates 16 kg boron per ha (Deora et al., 2014). The application of boron has earlier been tested in Danish trials prior to the millennia, and treatment of 1 to 2 kg per ha on a mildly infected field was found to exhibit an insignificant effect (Personal communication, SEGES 2015). Boron has demonstrated an evident potential to control clubroot disease, and renewed Danish trials of the soil amendment should be encouraged at application rates of 20 kg per ha.

3.4 Conclusion:

An integrated control is indubitable the most feasible strategy to achieve a successful management of clubroot disease in Denmark (Donald and Porter, 2009). None of the soil amendments or resistant cultivars exhibited a neither comprehensive nor reliable control of clubroot disease. A cultivation of WR should therefore be conducted in a precautionary 1 in 5 crop rotation design excluding susceptible break and MFO crops. Drainage of fields exposed to waterlogging should be maintained as good husbandry, equally impairing the ability of *P. brassicae* zoospores to seek a host. Usage of liming practices to establish a soil pH above 7.2 and concurrent increase calcium concentration exhibit a potential to reduce disease severity. Foreign studies on boron amendment equivalently show promising results and Danish trials should be encouraged. Deployment of resistant cultivars provide the uppermost control of clubroot, nonetheless it should be limited to moderately infested soils to prolong the durability of resistance in the available assortment (Personal communication, SEGES 2015). Lastly, a sufficient hygiene practices to confine the pathogen from further spread should be commonly introduced, alongside later sowing dates in warm moist autumns.

Conclusion

Reviewing the current knowledge on clubroot caused by *Plasmodiophora brassicae* in Danish winter rapeseed cultivation, following conclusions has been acquired in this literary study:

- ❖ Clubroot incidence is a mounting issue in Danish winter rapeseed production, capable of inflicting yield losses beyond 50%.
- ❖ *Plasmodiophora brassicae*, is presently classified as a protist specie of the supergroup Rhizaria.
- ❖ *Plasmodiophora brassicae* is a highly persistent pathogen capable of infecting a multitude of agricultural important crops, break crops, common weeds and enduring more than 17 years in the soil.

- ❖ *Plasmodiophora brassicae* induces phytohormone manipulation of the host carbon metabolism and physiological processes by predominantly auxins and cytokinins, leading to root gall development.
- ❖ Novel protocol in Real-time PCR enables a highly sensitive detection and quantification of *P. brassicae* in soil. Analysis is conducted by Eurofins Steins laboratory at 2500 DKK per sample.
- ❖ Utilizing serological techniques, a monoclonal antibody based lateral flow device exhibit potential as an rapid and inexpensive on-farm diagnostic test in near future.
- ❖ No single control measure can obtain a complete control of clubroot, an efficient control therefore rely on an integrated management strategy applying liming practices, drainage, crop rotation, resistant cultivars, and proper sanitary measures.
- ❖ Economic uncertain climate in Danish agriculture and unawareness of clubroot seemingly restrain farmers from investing in long-term management strategies such as drainage and liming practices.
- ❖ Present management strategy of clubroot is unsustainable, depending solely on a precautionary 1 in 5 crop rotation, and deployment of resistant cultivars.
- ❖ Declining control efficacy in resistant cultivars demands a restrained usage and emphasizes the necessity of novel cultivars.
- ❖ Several large-scale breeding companies are working to develop novel resistant winter rapeseed cultivars, presumably put on market in the near future.
- ❖ Finally, a comprehensive national investigation of clubroot incidence in Denmark is emphasized as a precautionary measure to facilitate a timely large-scale address to the issue if necessary.

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